

Soil organic matter and carbon stocks in soils on binary sediments

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Measurement of SOM content and stocks is one of the most important characteristics of soil organic matter in terrestrial ecosystems. Considering that soils on two-membered deposits are quite widespread in the territory of the European North-East (including the territory of the Komi Republic), this work assesses the SOC stocks in organogenic horizons and in the soil profile as a whole in this type of soil, developed in different conditions of hydromorphism and under different types of forest.

The study focused on soils from the Lyalsky test site (62°15' N, 50°40' E). The site was created in the Komi Republic as part of the Unified National System for Monitoring Climate-Active Substances project. Within the testing area, 30 sample plots (SP) have been established, which are conditionally assigned to 6 groups of forest types: 1 – small-leaved herbaceous, dwarf shrub, and herbaceous-dwarf shrub birch and aspen forests; 2 – herbaceous spruce forests; 3 – dwarf shrub-green moss spruce forests, including dwarf shrub-long-moss spruce forests; 4 – dwarf shrub-sphagnum spruce forests, including grass-sphagnum spruce forests; 5 – dwarf shrub-green moss pine forests; 6 – dwarf shrub-sphagnum pine forests. The soil cover of the considered SPs is represented by various types and subtypes of alfehumus and eluvial soils. When assessing SOC stocks, subhorizons of forest litter with a SOC content of > 20% were classified as organogenic horizons; with a SOC content of < 20%, they were classified as organo-mineral and taken into account in the composition of the mineral part of the profile.

The morphological and chemical characteristics of soil organic matter (SOM) vary widely in soils on binary deposits (sands underlain by loams). This is due to differences in the structure of the vegetation cover, the composition of plant litter, moisture conditions, the nature of the underlying rocks, topography, and microbiota activity.

Organogenic horizons in soils of small-leaved forests, as well as grassy and green moss spruce forests, are characterized by relatively thin (5–6 cm) organic horizons, with stocks ranging from 37–54 t/ha. Green moss pine forests accumulate thicker (12 cm) organic matter, with reserves of up to 73 t/ha. Increasing soil moisture in sphagnum forest types contributes to an increase in the organic matter thickness to 15–17 cm, and reserves to 85–105 t/ha. An assessment of carbon stocks in organogenic horizons and a meter-thick soil profile revealed that carbon stocks in organic horizons vary depending on forest type, ranging from 12.8 ± 2.1 to 64.0 ± 7.9 t/ha, while in the meter-thick soil profile, they range from 78.3 ± 7.0 to 133.9 ± 14.0 t/ha. Of the total organic carbon stocks accumulated in the meter-thick soil profile, organic horizons account for up to 15–40% in automorphic soils and up to 49% in semihydromorphic soils.

In soils of forest communities occupying automorphic relief positions, the thickness and reserves of organic matter decrease in the order near-trunk elevation → under-crown space → inter-crown space. In sphagnum forest types, the opposite trend is observed, which may be due to the drainage influence of trees and microrelief features.

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